

ISic4380

Fragmentary Greek epitaph

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Excavated (between 1990 and 2012) in the southern necropolis, in re-use as the cover of an ash-chest in t.1, Isolato 96, II Comparto, via degli Orti

Coordinates

38.183646, 15.549568

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Soprintendenza stores, inventory ME 22799

Physical Description

Right half of a limestone plaque. The left half is missing, minor damage to the upper and right edges. The reverse is rough. Remains of an iron nail in the upper edge rear edge, and traces of a metal clamp on the upper margin

Dimensions

Height 24.8 cm

Width 30.5 cm

Depth 6 cm

Layout

Remains of five lines of Greek letters, apparently centered on the stone, with incised guidelines. The final line is significantly smaller. The outline of a human hand is incised on the lower right below the text.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Lunate letters, with the later minuscule style of mu. Letters are regular and neatly v-cut, with minimal serifs. Heart-shaped hedera at end of line 4 after the age.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-5: 35 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]ς ναυ
2. [---]εικομη
3. [---]ἔζησεν
4. [---][ἔτη] μγ
5. [---]λεπει

Apparatus

Text after Zavettieri 2017

Translation (en)

[...] lived 43 years [...]

Translation (it)

[...]visse anni 43 [...]

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Zavettieri, G. 2017. Le epigrafi. In Tigano, G.(eds.), *Da Zancle a Messina 2016. Nuovi dati di archeologia urbana*. Palermo. pp. 167-171. At 169 no.3 fig.3

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archivio fotografico della soprintendenza di Messina

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